

ABOUT HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Annotation. It is said that it is easy to learn and maintain bad habits but it is very difficult to switch them back. The issue of a healthy lifestyle is very serious but the people take it very lightly. Often, it is seen that the people take steps to improve their lifestyle but due to lack of determination quits in the midway.

Moreover, for a healthy lifestyle is it important that you take small and one-step at a time. Also, do not go overboard with it. Besides, this healthy lifestyle will help you in life in a lot of ways.

Аннотация. Говорят, что легко научиться и сохранить вредные привычки, но очень трудно вернуть их обратно. Вопрос здорового образа жизни очень серьезный, но люди относятся к нему очень легкомысленно. Часто видно, что люди предпринимают шаги по улучшению своего образа жизни, но из-за отсутствия решимости останавливаются на полпути.

Более того, для здорового образа жизни важно, чтобы вы делали понемногу и по одному шагу за раз. Также не стоит перебарщивать с ним. Кроме того, этот здоровый образ жизни во многом поможет вам в жизни.

Key words: healthy lifestyle, diet, essential minerals and vitamins, healthy habit, body, benefits, sickness and diseases, physical health.

Ключевые слова: здоровый образ жизни, диета, необходимые минералы и витамины, организм, польза, болезни, физическое здоровье.

Habits that keeps you healthy: For keeping your body and mind healthy you have to follow certain rules that will help you achieve your goal. Besides, there are certain measures that will help you to stay healthy.

First of all, for being healthy you have to plan and follow a strict diet. This diet should contain all the essential minerals and vitamins required by the body. Also, eat only healthy food and avoid junk and heavily carbohydrate and fatty food.

In addition, wake up early in the morning because first of all, it's a healthy habit. Secondly, waking up early means you can get ready for your work early, spend some quality time with your family. Besides, this decides time for your sleep and sleep early because it de-stresses body.¹

Doing exercise regularly makes your body more active and it also releases the pent-up stress from the muscles.

Avoid the mobile- the biggest drawback of this generation is that they are obsessed with their mobile phones. Moreover, these phones cause many physical and mental problem for them. So, to avoid the negative effects of mobile the usage volume of them should be reduced.

¹ <https://www.plustopper.com>.

Connecting with positive minds because the more you indulge with these people then less you will go to the negative side.²

A healthy lifestyle has many benefits not only for the body but for the mind too. Also, if you follow a healthy lifestyle then you can reduce the risk of having cancer, heart disease, diabetes, obesity, and osteoporosis.

To sum it up, we can say that there are various benefits of living a healthy lifestyle. Also, a healthy lifestyle has many benefits to your social as well as personal life. Besides, it improves the relationships in the family. Most importantly, the person who lives a healthy lifestyle lives longer as compared to those who do not.

A healthy lifestyle involves a lot of things under it, including a nutritional diet, daily exercise, adequate sleep, being happy, and thinking positively. When we do all the necessary elements to have a healthy lifestyle, our lives are going on the right path. Living a healthy life is vital for you to be happy and feel good in your present life and for the future. Once you choose to live a healthy life, it lasts all your life. It not only helps you live longer but also better and less prone to sickness and diseases. A healthy lifestyle is the kind of lifestyle that we should all strive for.

Having a healthy lifestyle is all about choosing to live your life in the most healthy way possible. There are a few things you have to do to start living your life in this way, i.e., the healthy way. This means doing some amount of exercise daily, such as jogging, yoga, playing sports, etc. Adding to this, you must also have a balanced and nutritional diet with all the food groups. It would be best if you were taking the right amount of proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals, and fats to help you have a proper diet. Grouped with these two essential aspects (diet and exercise), a healthy person also maintains the same sleep cycle, which should consist of around 7-8 hours of sleep. However, we must remember that a healthy lifestyle not only refers to our physical and mental health. Maintaining a balanced diet, exercising daily, and sleeping well are essential parts of a healthy lifestyle. But feeling happy is also a big part of a healthy lifestyle. To enable happiness, thinking positively is a must. When a person does not feel happy or good about themselves, they are not entirely healthy. Thus we must do our best to think positively so that we can feel happy rather than sad.³

We have talked about what all entails a healthy life, so now we must speak of what all does not. There are several things that one must avoid in order to live a healthy lifestyle. These include the kind of practices and habits that are harmful to us and also to the people around us, i.e., society. Such practices and habits include gambling, smoking, drinking, illegal drugs, or any other things that can turn into an addiction. These habits are harmful to not only you but for all the people around you, as addiction causes unhealthy attitudes and behaviors. Other unhealthy practices include skipping meals and eating junk food.

10 lines about healthy lifestyle

1. Exercise daily by running, jogging, playing sports, dancing or brisk walking
2. Eat three nutritional meals a day with all the food groups (carbohydrates, proteins, fats, vitamins, and minerals)
3. Make sure to get enough sleep, i.e., 7-8 hours per night
4. Don't sleep too much or too less, because either can lead to fatigue
5. Mental health is as important as physical health for a healthy lifestyle

² <https://gradesfixer.com>.

³ <https://www.toppr.com>.

6. Once you start living a healthy lifestyle, there's no turning back to old, unhealthy ways
7. Avoid harmful habits like smoking, drinking, drugs, gambling, etc.
8. A healthy lifestyle helps you live longer
9. Healthy living reduces your risk of life-threatening diseases like cancer and diabetes, among others
10. You will be grateful later in life for practicing a healthy lifestyle as well as now
Making changes to improve your health can lead to benefits for your body, your mind, your wallet, and even the environment.

1. Prevents disease. Healthy habits can reduce the risk of various diseases, including those that may run in your family.

For example, in a recent study, adults who followed a standard American diet (rich in fruits and vegetables) for 8 weeks had a reduced risk of cardiovascular disease. In another 2020 study Trusted Source, researchers found that every 66-gram increase in daily fruit and vegetable intake was associated with a 25 percent lower risk of developing type 2 diabetes.

Swapping out some refined grains for whole grains also reduces the risk of disease. In an observational study Trusted Source of almost 200,000 adults, those who ate the most whole grains had a 29 percent lower rate of type 2 diabetes than those who ate the least.

And a review Trusted Source of 45 studies concluded that eating 90 grams (or three 30-gram servings) of whole grains daily reduced the risk of cardiovascular disease by 22 percent, coronary heart disease by 19 percent, and cancer by 15 percent.

In terms of exercise, as little as 11 minutes a day may add years to your life. In a 2020 study, researchers tracked more than 44,000 adults. Those who got 11 minutes of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity each day had a lower risk of death compared to those who only exercised at that intensity for 2 minutes. This comparison held true even if people sat for 8.5 hours every day.

2. Saves money

It's always smart to see your primary care physician for an annual physical exam. This is especially true seeing how some health conditions, such as high blood pressure, are "silent." This means they don't have any symptoms, so unless you are checked, you usually don't know you have the condition. However, the healthier you are, the less likely you will have to see a doctor. This could save money by reducing co-pays, the need for prescriptions, and other treatments.

3. Lengthens lifespan

Basic healthy habits are connected with living a longer life. If, at age 50, you've never smoked, maintain a healthy weight, are regularly active, follow a healthy diet, and keep alcohol to a moderate consumption, you could live up to 14 years Trusted Source longer. Making even a few of these changes could lengthen your lifespan.

4. It can be good for the environment

Ultra-processed foods are those that contain refined grains and additives to change the texture, taste, or color. Some examples of these foods are cheese puffs, packaged dessert cakes, chicken nuggets, and sweetened breakfast cereals. More than 70 percent of foods in U.S. supermarkets are ultra-processed. The making of ultra-processed foods contributes to greenhouse gas emissions, water scarcity, decreased biodiversity, plastic waste, and deforestation.⁴

⁴ <https://www.health.harvard.edu>.

However, there are easy fixes for this. For example, if every person cut their weekly beef consumption by 1/4 pound, the decrease in global warming gas emissions would be the equivalent of taking four to six million cars off the road, according to the National Resources Defense Council.

But it's not only about what you eat more or less of. Replacing short car rides with biking can also cut back on the amount of carbon dioxide released into the atmosphere.

In a non-peer reviewed 2010 study, researchers estimated that if 20 percent of citizens in Madison, Wisconsin biked for trips less than 5 miles, it would reduce carbon dioxide emissions by more than 57,000 tons each year. And, a 2017 study in Stockholm found that, if drivers who lived within a half-hour bike ride to and from work commuted by bike rather than car, it could save 449 years of life annually in the county due to reduced vehicle emission.

These estimates aren't simply dreams. Barcelona's bike-share program reduces emissions of carbon dioxide by about 10,000 tons each year Trusted Source.

References:

1. <https://www.plustopper.com>.
2. <https://gradesfixer.com>.
3. <https://www.toppr.com>.
4. <https://www.health.harvard.edu>.